

The Structure of Neutrosophic Radical of an ideal and Primary Ideal in Neutrosophic Rings

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Abstract:

In this study, we define radical and primary ideals as novel types of neutrosophic substructures within a neutrosophic ring. We investigate the properties of these substructures based on the characteristics of neutrosophic rings. Finally, several examples are provided to illustrate the validity of the results. Although neutrosophic radical and primary ideals have intrinsic theoretical value, this study aims to lay the groundwork for establishing a Noether theorem on neutrosophic primary decompositions.

Keywords: Neutrosophic ring, Neutrosophic primary, Neutrosophic Radical, Ideal.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophy represents an advanced understanding of intuitionistic fuzzy logic. This concept has significant implications for decision-making processes [1] and medical studies [2]. The applications of neutrosophy have been further explored in [3,4,5,6,7]. As a novel branch of philosophy, neutrosophy can be adapted to algebraic structures, thereby enabling a deeper comprehension and further development of these structures.

The neutrosophic concept was first introduced by Smarandache in 1980. Neutrosophic structures represent a recent addition to the classification of algebraic structures, with numerous applications and developments reported, such as neutrosophic topologies [8,9] and neutrosophic rings [10,11,12,13].

Neutrosophic rings exhibit several intriguing characteristics and substructures, such as neutrosophic subrings and ideals. Extensive definitions and studies have been carried out on these structures [14,15,16]. In [17], the notion of the root of an AH-ideal was introduced. Abobala investigated the concept of maximal and minimal ideals in neutrosophic rings [18]. Alabdullah studied the concept of prime and completely prime ideals of neutrosophic rings [19].

In this study, we focus on ideals with the form $P + QI$, where $P \subseteq Q$ are ideals within the classical ring. Building upon the preceding concept, two novel types of neutrosophic substructures, namely radical ideals and primary ideals are introduced. Several theorems are established, describing their fundamental properties, which are both intriguing and analogous to those of classical radical and primary ideals, albeit with certain distinctions.

This study aims to address a significant research gap by identifying and characterizing all radical and primary ideals within neutrosophic rings. Furthermore, it will contribute to the classification of specific types of neutrosophic rings, such as Noetherian and Artinian rings.

2. Definitions and notations

Since researchers interested in classical rings already possess comprehensive knowledge of them and their ideals, this part presents neutrosophic rings and the properties of their ideals.

Definition 2.1 [11] Assume that R is a ring. The collection $R(I) = \{a + bI ; a, b \in R \text{ and } I^2 = I\}$ is called a neutrosophic ring. When R is a field, $R(I)$ is a neutrosophic field.

Properties 2.2 [11]

1. A ring R is a unity commutative ring iff $R(I)$ is a unity commutative neutrosophic ring with neutrosophic unity I .
2. $I^m = I, \forall m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$
3. $xI = Ix, \forall x \in R$.
4. $0I = 0$ and $\underbrace{I + I + \dots + I}_{m \text{ time}} = mI$

Definition 2.3 [11]

If $\emptyset \neq J \subseteq R(I)$, J is called a neutrosophic ideal if it is a neutrosophic subring of $R(I)$ and $xj, jx \in J$ for each $j \in J$ and $x \in R(I)$.

Theorem 2.4 [18]

If $J + KI \subseteq R(I)$, then $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic ideal iff J and K are ideals in R , where $J \subseteq K$.

Theorem 2.5 [18]

If $J + KI$ is an ideal in $R(I)$, $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic maximal ideal iff J is a maximal ideal of R , where $K = R$ or $J + KI = R(I)$.

Definition 2.6 [19] Assume that $R(I)$ is a neutrosophic ring and that $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$.

1. $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic prime if it satisfies the following condition:

$$\forall J_1 + K_1I, J_2 + K_2I \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}; J_1 \subseteq K_1 \text{ and } J_2 \subseteq K_2;$$

$$(J_1 + K_1I)(J_2 + K_2I) \subseteq J + KI$$

$$\Rightarrow J_1 + K_1I \subseteq J + KI \text{ or } J_2 + K_2I \subseteq J + KI$$

2. $J + KI$ is a completely prime if it satisfies the following condition:

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall r_1 + r_2I \text{ and } r_3 + r_4I \in R(I); (r_1 + r_2I)(r_3 + r_4I) \in J + KI \\ &\Rightarrow r_1 + r_2I \in J + KI \vee r_3 + r_4I \in J + KI \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.7 [19] Assume that $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$. If $J + KI \in N\wp_{R(I)}$, then J and $K \in \wp_R$.

Theorem 2.8 [19] Assume that $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$. If $J + KI \in NC\wp_{R(I)}$, then J and $K \in C\wp_R$.

Theorem 2.9 [19] Assume that $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$, $J + KI \in NC\wp_{R(I)}$, then $J + KI \in N\wp_{R(I)}$.

Theorem 2.10 [19] If $R(I)$ is a unity and $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$, $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic prime iff it satisfies the following condition:

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall r_1 + r_2I \text{ and } r_3 + r_4I \in R(I); (r_1 + r_2I)R(I)(r_3 + r_4I) \subseteq J + KI \\ &\Rightarrow r_1 + r_2I \in J + KI \text{ or } r_3 + r_4I \in J + KI \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.11 [19] Assume that $R(I)$ is a commutative neutrosophic ring with unity.

If $J + KI \in N\wp_{R(I)}$, then $J + KI \in NC\wp_{R(I)}$.

Definition 2.12 [17]

Assume that $R(I)$ is a neutrosophic ring, and let $P = P_0 + P_1I = \{a_0 + a_1I; a_0 \in P_0, a_1 \in P_1\}$. Then P is called an AH-ideal if P_0 and P_1 are ideals in R .

Definition 2.13 [17] Assume that $R(I)$ is a commutative and that $P = P_0 + P_1I$ is an AH-ideal. Then the AH-root of P can be defined as: $AH - Rad(P) = \sqrt{P_0} + \sqrt{P_1}I$.

We denote by $N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$ the collection of all neutrosophic ideals of $R(I)$. Moreover, we use $(N\wp_{R(I)}, NC\wp_{R(I)}, NG\wp_{R(I)}, N\wp_{R(I)})$ to denote the collections of neutrosophic (prime, completely prime, generalized primary, primary) ideals, respectively. In the classical ring R , we denote the collection of all ideals by \mathfrak{I}_R , and the collections of (prime, completely prime, generalized primary, primary) ideals by $(\wp_R, C\wp_R, G\wp_R, \wp_R)$, respectively. Throughout this paper, $R(I)$ is assumed to be a neutrosophic ring with unity.

3. Radical of Neutrosophic Ideals

Theorem 3.1 Assume that $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$. Then $J + KI \in N\wp_{R(I)}$ iff $J \in \wp_R$ and $K = R$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) if $J + KI \in N\wp_{R(I)}$, then both J and $K \in \wp_R$, according to Theorem 2.7.

Now, we proceed to show that $K = R$. Suppose that $k \in K$

We have I and $1 + (k - 1)I \in R(I)$.

On the other hand, we note

$$IR(I) [1 + (k - 1)I] = RI[1 + (k - 1)I] = R[I + kl - I] = 0 + Rkl \subseteq J + KI$$

Since $J + KI \in N\wp_{R(I)}$, it follows from Theorem 2.10 that either $I \in J + KI$ or $1 + (k - 1)I \in J + KI$.

Suppose first that $I \in J + KI$. Then $I \in KI \Rightarrow 1 \in K$. Hence, $K = R$.

Now suppose that $1 + (k - 1)I \in J + KI$. Then, $1 \in J \subseteq K$, and therefore $K = R$.

In both cases, we conclude that $K = R$.

(\Leftarrow): Suppose that $J \in \wp \mathfrak{R}_R$ and $K = R$.

Let $J_1 + K_1I, J_2 + K_2I; J_1 \subseteq K_1$ and $J_2 \subseteq K_2$ be neutrosophic ideals of $R(I)$, such that:

$$\begin{aligned} (J_1 + K_1I)(J_2 + K_2I) &\subseteq J + RI \\ \Rightarrow J_1J_2 + (J_1K_2 + K_1J_2 + K_1K_2)I &\subseteq J + RI \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $J_1J_2 \subseteq J$ and $J_1K_2 + K_1J_2 + K_1K_2 \subseteq R$.

Since J is the prime ideal, either $J_1 \subseteq J$ or $J_2 \subseteq J$.

If $J_1 \subseteq J$, then $J_1 + K_1I \subseteq J + RI$. Similarly, if $J_2 \subseteq J$, then $J_2 + K_2I \subseteq J + RI$.

Therefore, $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic prime.

Theorem 3.2 Assume that $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{T}_{R(I)}$. Then $J + KI \in NC\wp_{R(I)}$ iff $J \in C\wp_R$ and $K = R$.

Proof.

In a way analogous to the proof of Theorem 3.1.

Definition 3.3 Assuming that $R(I)$ is a neutrosophic ring and $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{T}_{R(I)}$.

We define the radical of ideal $J + KI$ as follows:

$$Rad(J + KI) = \sqrt{J + KI} = \{r_1 + r_2I \in R(I); (r_1 + r_2I)^n \in J + KI, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$$

Theorem 3.4 Assume $R(I)$ is a neutrosophic ring and that $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{T}_{R(I)}$. Then

$r_1 + r_2I \in \sqrt{J + KI}$ iff $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; r_1^n \in J$ and $(r_1 + r_2)^n \in K$; (equivalently, $r_1 \in \sqrt{J}$ and $r_1 + r_2 \in \sqrt{K}$).

Proof.

(\Rightarrow): Suppose that $r_1 + r_2I \in \sqrt{J + KI}$. Then, by Definition 3.3, we have $r_1 + r_2I \in R(I)$ and $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (r_1 + r_2I)^n \in J + KI$.

$$\Rightarrow (r_1 + r_2I)^n = r_1^n + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n r_1^{n-i} r_2^i\right)I \in J + KI \Rightarrow r_1^n \in J \subseteq K \text{ and } \left(\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n r_1^{n-i} r_2^i\right) \in K$$

$$\Rightarrow r_1^n \in J \subseteq K \text{ and } r_1^n + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n r_1^{n-i} r_2^i\right) = (r_1 + r_2)^n \in K$$

$$\Rightarrow r_1 \in \sqrt{J} \text{ and } r_1 + r_2 \in \sqrt{K}$$

(\Leftarrow): Suppose that $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; r_1^n \in J$ and $(r_1 + r_2)^n \in K$.

$$\Rightarrow r_1^n \in J \subseteq K \text{ and } (r_1 + r_2)^n = r_1^n + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n r_1^{n-i} r_2^i \right) \in K \Rightarrow -r_1^n + r_1^n + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n r_1^{n-i} r_2^i \right) = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n r_1^{n-i} r_2^i \in K$$

On the other hand, we have

$$(r_1 + r_2 I)^n = r_1^n + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n r_1^{n-i} r_2^i \right) I \in J + KI$$

Therefore, by Definition 3.3, we conclude that $r_1 + r_2 I \in \sqrt{J + KI}$.

Corollary 3.5 If $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{R}(I)$, then $\sqrt{J + KI} = \sqrt{J} + \sqrt{KI}$.

Proof.

$\forall r_1 + r_2 I \in \sqrt{J + KI} \Rightarrow r_1 \in \sqrt{J}$ and $r_1 + r_2 \in \sqrt{K}$ by Theorem 3.4. Since $J \subseteq K$, it follows that $\sqrt{J} \subseteq \sqrt{K}$. Now, since $r_1 \in \sqrt{J} \subseteq \sqrt{K}$

Since $r_1 \in \sqrt{J} \subseteq \sqrt{K}$, we also have $-r_1 \in \sqrt{K}$. Therefore, $r_1 \in \sqrt{J}$ and $r_2 \in \sqrt{K}$. Hence, $\sqrt{J + KI} \subseteq \sqrt{J} + \sqrt{KI}$.

Conversely, $\forall r_1 + r_2 I \in \sqrt{J} + \sqrt{KI} \Rightarrow r_1 \in \sqrt{J} \subseteq \sqrt{K}$ and $r_2 \in \sqrt{K} \Rightarrow r_1 + r_2 \in \sqrt{K}$

By Theorem 3.4, it follows that $r_1 + r_2 I \in \sqrt{J + KI}$. Therefore, $\sqrt{J} + \sqrt{KI} \subseteq \sqrt{J + KI}$.

Thus, equality is achieved.

Corollary 3.6 It is clear from Corollary 3.5 that radical of any ideal $J + KI$ is also an $AH - Rad(J + KI)$.

Theorem 3.7 Assume that $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{R}(I)$. Then $\sqrt{J + KI} \in N\mathfrak{R}(I); J + KI \subseteq \sqrt{J + KI}$.

Proof.

First, by Theorem 3.5, we have $\sqrt{J + KI} = \sqrt{J} + \sqrt{KI}$. Moreover, \sqrt{J} is an ideal containing J , and \sqrt{K} is an ideal containing K . Therefore, $\sqrt{J} + \sqrt{KI}$ is an ideal containing $J + KI$.

Corollary 3.8 The neutrosophic nilpotent elements in $R(I)$ are given by $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle + \langle 0 \rangle I} = \{r_1 + r_2 I \in R(I); (r_1 + r_2 I)^n = 0, n \in \mathbb{Z}^+\}$.

Examples 3.9

(1) In $\mathbb{Z}_6(I)$, we have $\sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I} = \{r_1 + r_2 I \in \mathbb{Z}_6(I); r_1 \in \sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle} \text{ and } r_2 \in \sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle}\}$ by Corollary 3.5.

Since $\langle 3 \rangle \in \wp_{\mathbb{Z}_6}$, it follows that $\sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle} = \langle 3 \rangle = \{0, 3\}$. Therefore, $\sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I} = \{0, 0, 3, 3I, 3 + 3I\} = \langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I$. It is clear that $\sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I} \in N\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}_6(I)}$ and $\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I \subseteq \sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I}$.

(2) In $\mathbb{Z}(I)$, we have $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I} = \{r_1 + r_2 I \in \mathbb{Z}(I); r_1 \in \sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle} \text{ and } r_2 \in \sqrt{\langle 2 \rangle}\}$ by Corollary 3.5.

Since $\langle 0 \rangle$ and $\langle 2 \rangle \in \wp_{\mathbb{Z}}$, it follows that $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle} = \{0\}$ and $\sqrt{\langle 2 \rangle} = \langle 2 \rangle$. Therefore, $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I} = \langle 0 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I$.

It is clear that $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I} \in N\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}(I)}$ and $\langle 0 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I \subseteq \sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I}$.

(3) In $\mathbb{Z}_5(I)$, we have $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle} + \langle 1 \rangle I = \{r_1 + r_2 I \in \mathbb{Z}_5(I); r_1 \sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle} \text{ and } r_2 \in \sqrt{\langle 1 \rangle}\}$ by Corollary 3.5. Since $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle} = \{0\}$ and $\sqrt{\langle 1 \rangle} = \langle 1 \rangle = \mathbb{Z}_5$, it follows that $\sqrt{\langle 0 \rangle} + \langle 1 \rangle I = \langle 0 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I = \mathbb{Z}_5 I$.

Corollary 3.10 If $J_1 + K_1 I$ and $J_2 + K_2 I \in N\mathfrak{A}_{R(I)}$, then:

1. $J_1 + K_1 I \subseteq J_2 + K_2 I \Rightarrow \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \subseteq \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I}$
2. $\sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I)} = \sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I)} = \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \cap \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I}$
3. $\sqrt{\sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I}} = \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I}$
4. $\sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I) + (J_2 + K_2 I)} = \sqrt{\sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} + \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I}}$

Proof.

(1) $\forall j_1 + k_1 I \in \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \Rightarrow \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (j_1 + k_1 I)^n \in J_1 + K_1 I \subseteq J_2 + K_2 I \Rightarrow j_1 + k_1 I \in \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I} \Rightarrow \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \subseteq \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I}$

(2) We have $(J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I) \subseteq J_1 + K_1 I$ and $(J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I) \subseteq J_2 + K_2 I \Rightarrow (J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I) \subseteq (J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I)$

Hence, by (1), we obtain $\sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I)} \subseteq \sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I)} \dots \dots (i)$

On the other hand,

$$(J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I) \subseteq J_1 + K_1 I \text{ and } (J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I) \subseteq J_2 + K_2 I$$

Hence, by (1), we obtain $\sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I)} \subseteq \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I}$ and $\sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I)} \subseteq \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I}$

$$\Rightarrow \sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I)} \subseteq \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \cap \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I} \dots \dots (ii)$$

From (i) and (ii), we obtain $\sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I)} \subseteq \sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I) \cap (J_2 + K_2 I)} \subseteq \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \cap \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I}$

Now, let us prove that $\sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \cap \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I} \subseteq \sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I)}$.

$$\forall s + tI \in \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \cap \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I} \Rightarrow s + tI \in \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} \text{ and } s + tI \in \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I} \Rightarrow \exists m, l \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (s + tI)^m \in J_1 + K_1 I \text{ and } (s + tI)^l \in J_2 + K_2 I$$

$$\Rightarrow (s + tI)^m (s + tI)^l \in (J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I) \Rightarrow (s + tI)^{m+l} \in (J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I); m + l \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \Rightarrow s + tI \in \sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I)}$$

Thus, equality is achieved.

(3) According to Corollary 3.5, we have $\sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} = \sqrt{\sqrt{J_1} + \sqrt{K_1} I} = \sqrt{\sqrt{J_1}} + \sqrt{\sqrt{K_1} I} = \sqrt{J_1} + \sqrt{K_1} I = \sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I}$.

(4) According to Corollary 3.5, we have

$$\sqrt{(J_1 + K_1 I) + (J_2 + K_2 I)} = \sqrt{(J_1 + J_2) + (K_1 + K_2) I} = \sqrt{J_1 + J_2} + \sqrt{K_1 + K_2} I \dots \dots (i)$$

On the other hand,

$$\sqrt{\sqrt{J_1 + K_1 I} + \sqrt{J_2 + K_2 I}} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{J_1} + \sqrt{K_1} I) + (\sqrt{J_2} + \sqrt{K_2} I)} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{J_1} + \sqrt{J_2}) + (\sqrt{K_1} + \sqrt{K_2}) I} = \sqrt{(\sqrt{J_1} + \sqrt{J_2})} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{K_1} + \sqrt{K_2}) I} = \sqrt{J_1 + J_2} + \sqrt{K_1 + K_2} I \dots \dots (ii)$$

From (i) and (ii), equality is achieved.

Example 3.11

(1) In $\mathbb{Z}(I)$, we have $\langle 16 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I \subseteq \langle 8 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I$.

First, we note $\sqrt{\langle 16 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I} = \{r_1 + r_2 I \in \mathbb{Z}(I); r_1 \in \sqrt{\langle 16 \rangle} = \langle 2 \rangle \text{ and } r_2 \in \sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle} = \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I$.

On the other hand, we also have $\sqrt{\langle 8 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I} = \{r_1 + r_2 I \in \mathbb{Z}(I); r_1 \in \sqrt{\langle 8 \rangle} = \langle 2 \rangle \text{ and } r_2 \in \sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle} = \langle 2 \rangle\} = \langle 2 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I$. Therefore, it follows that $\sqrt{\langle 16 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I} \subseteq \sqrt{\langle 8 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I}$.

(2) In $\mathbb{Z}_6(I)$, we have $\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I$ and $\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I \in N\mathfrak{I}_{\mathbb{Z}_6(I)}$.

First, we note $\sqrt{(\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I) \cap (\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I)} = \sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I} = \langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I$.

On the other hand, we also have $\sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I} \cap \sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I} = (\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I) \cap (\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I) = \langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I$.

Finally, $\sqrt{(\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I)(\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I)} = \sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I} = \langle 3 \rangle + \langle 3 \rangle I$.

(3) In $\mathbb{Z}_8(I)$, we have $\sqrt{\sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I}} = \sqrt{\langle 2 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I} = \langle 2 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I = \sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I}$.

(4) In $\mathbb{Z}_6(I)$, we have $\sqrt{(\langle 2 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I) + (\langle 2 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I)} = \sqrt{\langle 2 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I} = \langle 2 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I$.

On the other hand, we have

$$\sqrt{\langle 2 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I} + \sqrt{\langle 2 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I} = (\langle 2 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I) + (\langle 2 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I) = \langle 2 \rangle + \langle 1 \rangle I.$$

Theorem 3.12 Assume that $S + TI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$. Then $S + TI \in NC\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$ iff $\sqrt{S + TI} = S + TI = S + RI$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow): According to Corollary 3.5, we have $\sqrt{S + TI} = \sqrt{S} + \sqrt{TI}$.

Since $S + TI \in NC\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$, it follows that $S \in \mathcal{C}\mathfrak{I}_{R'}$ and $T = R$, by Theorem 3.2.

Since $S \in \mathcal{C}\mathfrak{I}_{R'}$, it follows that $\sqrt{S} = S$. Thus, $\sqrt{S + TI} = \sqrt{S} + \sqrt{RI} = S + RI$.

(\Leftarrow): $\forall r_1 + r_2 I \in R(I); (r_1 + r_2 I)^2 \in S + TI \Rightarrow r_1 + r_2 I \in \sqrt{S + TI} = S + TI \Rightarrow r_1 + r_2 I \in S + TI$

Thus, $S + TI \in NC\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$.

Corollary 3.13 Assume that $R(I)$ is a commutative neutrosophic ring. Then $S + TI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$ iff $\sqrt{S + TI} = S + TI$.

Proof.

Since $R(I)$ is a commutative, the result follows directly from Corollary 2.11 and Theorem 3.12.

Example 3.14

We have $\langle 3 \rangle + Z_6 I = \{0,3\} + Z_6 I \in N\mathfrak{I}_{Z_6(I)}$, and we note that $\sqrt{\langle 3 \rangle + Z_6 I} = \langle 3 \rangle + Z_6 I$.

Corollary 3.15 If $J + KI \in NC\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$, then $\sqrt{(J + KI)^n} = J + KI \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Proof.

We apply the principle of mathematical induction. If $n = 1$, then by Theorem 3.12, we have $\sqrt{J + KI} = J + KI$.

Assume that for all $l \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ with $1 \leq l < n$, we have $\sqrt{(J + KI)^l} = J + KI$.

We now prove that the equality holds for $n = l + 1$, i.e., we show that $\sqrt{(J + KI)^{l+1}} = J + KI$.

Using Corollary 3.10, we obtain the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{(J + KI)^{l+1}} &= \sqrt{(J + KI)^l (J + KI)} = \sqrt{(J + KI)^l \cap (J + KI)} = \sqrt{(J + KI)^l} \cap \sqrt{(J + KI)} \\ &= (J + KI) \cap (J + KI) = J + KI \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.16 If $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic ideal in $R(I)$, then

$$\sqrt{J + KI} \subseteq \left\{ \bigcap_{l \in L} S_l + T_l I; S_l + T_l I \in NC\wp_{R(I)} \text{ and } J + KI \subseteq S_l + T_l I \right\}$$

Proof.

Since $J + KI \subseteq S_l + T_l I \forall l \in L$, it follows that $\sqrt{J + KI} \subseteq \sqrt{S_l + T_l I}$ according to Corollary 3.10.

On the other hand, we have $S_l + T_l I \in NC\wp_{R(I)}$, and by applying Theorem 3.12, we find that $\sqrt{S_l + T_l I} = S_l + T_l I$ for all $l \in L$. Therefore, $\sqrt{J + KI} \subseteq \bigcap_{l \in L} S_l + T_l I$.

Corollary 3.17 In fact, the equality in Theorem 3.15 does not necessarily hold in the general case.

Example 3.18

In $\mathbb{Z}(I)$, we have $\sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I} = \sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle} + \sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle} I = \langle 2 \rangle + \langle 2 \rangle I$.

On the other hand, we only have that $\langle 2 \rangle + \mathbb{Z}I \in NC\wp_{\mathbb{Z}(I)}$ containing $\sqrt{\langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I}$.

Theorem 3.19 If $J + RI$ is a neutrosophic ideal in $R(I)$, then

$$Rad(J + RI) = \sqrt{J + RI} = \left\{ \bigcap_{l \in L} S_l + RI; S_l \in C\wp_R \text{ and } J + RI \subseteq S_l + RI \right\}$$

Proof.

By Corollary 3.5, we have $\sqrt{J + RI} = \sqrt{J} + \sqrt{RI} = \sqrt{J} + RI$.

In R , we have $\sqrt{J} = \{ \bigcap_{l \in L} S_l; S_l \in C\wp_R \text{ and } J \subseteq S_l \}$. Therefore, in $R(I)$, we obtain $\sqrt{J} + RI =$

$$\{ \bigcap_{l \in L} S_l + RI; S_l \in C\wp_R \text{ and } J + RI \subseteq S_l + RI \}$$

Corollary 3.20 If $J + RI$ is a neutrosophic ideal in $R(I)$, then $\sqrt{J + RI}$ is the smallest completely prime ideal in $R(I)$ containing $J + RI$.

Proof.

Using Theorem 3.19, we have

$$\sqrt{J + RI} = \{ \bigcap_{l \in L} S_l + RI; S_l \in C\wp_R \text{ and } J + RI \subseteq S_l + RI \} \Rightarrow \sqrt{J + RI} \in NC\wp_{R(I)} \text{ and } J + RI \subseteq$$

$$\sqrt{J + RI}.$$

Assume $A + BI \in NC\wp_{R(I)}$ and $J + RI \subseteq A + BI \subseteq \sqrt{J + RI}$.

Using Corollary 3.10 and Theorem 3.12, we obtain $\sqrt{J + RI} \subseteq \sqrt{A + BI} \subseteq \sqrt{\sqrt{J + RI}} = \sqrt{J + RI}$,

which implies that $\sqrt{J + RI} = \sqrt{A + BI} = A + BI$. Thus, $\sqrt{J + RI}$ is the smallest completely prime ideal in $R(I)$ containing $J + RI$.

4. Neutrosophic Primary Ideal

Definition 4.1 If $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$, then $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic generalized primary ideal if it satisfies the following condition:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall J_1 + K_1 I, J_2 + K_2 I \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}; J_1 \subseteq K_1 \text{ and } J_2 \subseteq K_2; \\ (J_1 + K_1 I)(J_2 + K_2 I) \subseteq J + KI \\ \Rightarrow J_1 + K_1 I \subseteq J + KI \vee \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (J_2 + K_2 I)^n \subseteq J + KI \end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.2 If $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$, then $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic primary ideal if it satisfies the following condition:

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall r_1 + r_2I \text{ and } r_3 + r_4I \in R(I); (r_1 + r_2I)(r_3 + r_4I) \in J + KI \\ &\Rightarrow r_1 + r_2I \in J + KI \vee \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (r_3 + r_4I)^n \in J + KI \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.3 If $J + KI \in N\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$, then $J + KI \in NG\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$.

Proof.

Assume that $J + KI \in N\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$, and let $J_1 + K_1I, J_2 + K_2I \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$ such that, $(J_1 + K_1I)(J_2 + K_2I) \subseteq J + KI$. Now, if $J_1 + K_1I \not\subseteq J + KI$ and $\forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (J_2 + K_2I)^n \not\subseteq J + KI$, then $\exists j_1 + k_1I \in J_1 + K_1I$ and $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (j_2 + k_2I)^n \in (J_2 + K_2I)^n$ where $j_1 + k_1I \notin J + KI$ and $(j_2 + k_2I)^n \notin J + KI$.

On the other hand, we have

$$(j_1 + k_1I)(j_2 + k_2I)^n \in (J_1 + K_1I)(J_2 + K_2I)^n \subseteq (J_1 + K_1I)(J_2 + K_2I) \subseteq J + KI$$

Since $J + KI \in N\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$, it follows that $j_1 + k_1I \in J + KI$ or $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (j_2 + k_2I)^n \in J + KI$. This leads to a contradiction. Therefore,

$$J_1 + K_1I \subseteq J + KI \vee \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (J_2 + K_2I)^n \subseteq J + KI. \text{ Thus, } J + KI \in NG\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}.$$

Theorem 4.4 If $J + KI \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$, then $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic generalized primary ideal iff the following condition is satisfied:

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall r_1 + r_2I \text{ and } r_3 + r_4I \in R(I); (r_1 + r_2I)R(I)(r_3 + r_4I) \subseteq J + KI \\ &\Rightarrow r_1 + r_2I \in J + KI \text{ or } \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (r_3 + r_4I)^n \in J + KI \end{aligned}$$

Proof. (\Rightarrow): Assume that $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic generalized primary, we prove that it satisfies the corresponding condition.

$$\begin{aligned} &\forall r_1 + r_2I \text{ and } r_3 + r_4I \in R(I); (r_1 + r_2I)R(I)(r_3 + r_4I) \subseteq J + KI \\ &\Rightarrow (r_1 + r_2I)R(I)(r_3 + r_4I)R(I) \subseteq (J + KI)R(I) \subseteq J + KI \end{aligned}$$

Since $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic generalized primary, then either $(r_1 + r_2I)R(I) \subseteq J + KI$ or $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; [(r_3 + r_4I)R(I)]^n \subseteq J + KI$.

On the other hand, we have

$$r_1 + r_2I = (r_1 + r_2I).1 \in (r_1 + r_2I)R(I) \subseteq J + KI \Rightarrow r_1 + r_2I \in J + KI$$

Also, we have $[(r_3 + r_4I).1]^n \in [(r_3 + r_4I)R(I)]^n \subseteq J + KI \Rightarrow (r_3 + r_4I)^n \in J + KI$

(\Leftarrow): Assuming that the given condition is holds, we will now prove that $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic generalized primary.

Let $J_1 + K_1I$ and $J_2 + K_2I$ be neutrosophic ideals of $R(I)$ such that $(J_1 + K_1I)(J_2 + K_2I) \subseteq J + KI$.

Assume that $J_1 + K_1I \not\subseteq J + KI$ and $(J_2 + K_2I)^n \not\subseteq J + KI \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$; therefore, $\exists r_1 + r_2I \in J_1 + K_1I$, where, $r_1 + r_2I \notin J + KI$ and $\exists r_3 + r_4I \in J_2 + K_2I$; $(r_3 + r_4I)^n \in (J_2 + K_2I)^n$, where, $(r_3 + r_4I)^n \notin J + KI$; $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

On the other hand, we have

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 + r_2I \in J_1 + K_1I &\Rightarrow (r_1 + r_2I)R(I) \subseteq J_1 + K_1I \\ &\Rightarrow (r_1 + r_2I)R(I)(r_3 + r_4I) \subseteq (J_1 + K_1I)(r_3 + r_4I) \subseteq (J_1 + K_1I)(J_2 + K_2I) \subseteq J + KI \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $r_1 + r_2I \in J + KI$ or $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$; $(r_3 + r_4I)^n \in J + KI$. This leads to a contradiction. Thus, $J_1 + K_1I \subseteq J + KI$ or $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$; $(J_2 + K_2I)^n \subseteq J + KI$, hence $J + KI \in NG\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$.

Corollary 4.5 Assume that $R(I)$ is a commutative neutrosophic ring. If $J + KI \in NG\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$, then $J + KI \in N\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$.

Proof.

Suppose that $J + KI \in NG\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$, and $r_1 + r_2I$ and $r'_1 + r'_2I \in R(I)$; $(r_1 + r_2I)(r'_1 + r'_2I) \in J + KI$.

$$\Rightarrow (r_1 + r_2I)(r'_1 + r'_2I)R(I) \subseteq (J + KI)R(I) \subseteq J + KI$$

Because $R(I)$ is a commutative, $(r_1 + r_2I)R(I)(r'_1 + r'_2I) \subseteq J + KI$.

Using Theorem.4.4, we find that

$$r_1 + r_2I \in J + KI \text{ or } \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (r'_1 + r'_2I)^n \in J + KI. \text{ Thus, } J + KI \in N\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}.$$

Theorem 4.6 $J + KI \in NG\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)} \Leftrightarrow J \in G\wp\mathfrak{R}_R$ and $K = R$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) We assume that J_1 and J_2 are ideals of R such that $J_1 J_2 \subseteq J \subseteq K$.

We have $J_1 + J_1I, J_2 + J_2I \in N\mathfrak{I}_{R(I)}$, and

$$(J_1 + J_1I)(J_2 + J_2I) = J_1J_2 + (J_1J_2 + J_1J_2 + J_1J_2)I \subseteq J + KI$$

Since $J + KI \in NG\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$, so $J_1 + J_1I \subseteq J + KI$ or $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$; $(J_2 + J_2I)^n = J_2^n + (\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n J_2^{n-i} J_2^i)I \subseteq J + KI$.

Therefore, $J_1 \subseteq J \vee J_2^n \subseteq J$. Thus, $J \in G\wp\mathfrak{R}_R$. Now, let us prove that $K = R$. Suppose $k \in K$.

We have I and $1 + (k - 1)I \in R(I)$.

$$IR(I) [1 + (k - 1)I] = RI[1 + (k - 1)I] = R[I + kI - I] = 0 + RkI \subseteq J + KI$$

Because $J + KI \in NG\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$, $I \in J + KI$ or $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$; $[1 + (k - 1)I]^n \in J + KI$, according to Theorem 4.4.

If $I \in J + KI$, then $I \in KI$, and therefore $1 \in K$. Thus, $K = R$.

If $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$; $[1 + (k - 1)I]^n \in J + KI \Rightarrow 1 + [\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n (1)^{n-i} (k - 1)^i]I \in J + KI \Rightarrow 1 \in J \subseteq K$

$$\Rightarrow K = R$$

(\Leftarrow): Suppose that $J \in \mathcal{G}\wp\mathfrak{R}_R$ and $K = R$. Let $J_1 + K_1I, J_2 + K_2I; J_1 \subseteq K_1$ and $J_2 \subseteq K_2$ be neutrosophic ideals of $R(I)$ such that $(J_1 + K_1I)(J_2 + K_2I) \subseteq J + RI$.

$$\Rightarrow J_1J_2 + (J_1K_2 + K_1J_2 + K_1K_2)I \subseteq J + RI$$

$$\Rightarrow J_1J_2 \subseteq J \text{ and } J_1K_2 + K_1J_2 + K_1K_2 \subseteq R$$

Since $J \in \mathcal{G}\wp\mathfrak{R}_R$, it follows that either $J_1 \subseteq J$ or $\exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; J_2^n \subseteq J$.

If $J_1 \subseteq J \Rightarrow J_1 + K_1I \subseteq J + RI$.

If $J_2^n \subseteq J \Rightarrow (J_2 + K_2I)^n = J_2^n + (\sum_{i=1}^n C_i^n J_2^{n-i} K_2^i)I \subseteq J + RI$. Therefore, $J + KI \in \mathcal{N}\mathcal{G}\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)}$.

Theorem 4.7 $J + KI \in \mathcal{N}\wp\mathfrak{R}_{R(I)} \Leftrightarrow J \in \wp\mathfrak{R}_R$ and $K = R$.

Proof.

In a manner comparable to the proof of Theorem 4.6.

Examples 4.8

(1) In \mathbb{Z} , we have $\langle 8 \rangle$ and $\langle 4 \rangle \in \wp\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}}$. However, $\langle 8 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I \notin \mathcal{N}\wp\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}(I)}$. To see this, consider the elements $0 + 3I$ and $1 + 7I \in \mathbb{Z}(I)$. We have $(0 + 3I)(1 + 7I) = 0 + 24I \in \langle 8 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I$. Nevertheless,

$$3I \text{ and } (1 + 7I)^n \notin \langle 8 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ [1 + 7I \text{ and } (3I)^n \notin \langle 8 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+].$$

Therefore, $\langle 8 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I \notin \mathcal{N}\wp\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}(I)}$.

(2) In \mathbb{Z}_{12} , the ideal $\langle 4 \rangle$ is primary. However, the ideal $\langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I$ is not primary $\mathbb{Z}_{12}(I)$.

To see this, consider the elements $5I$ and $1 + 3I \in \mathbb{Z}_{12}(I)$. We have $5I(1 + 3I) = 8I \in \langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I$

However, $5I \notin \langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I$ and $(1 + 3I)^n \notin \langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \{1 + 3I \notin \langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I$ and $(5I)^n \notin \langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \}$. Therefore, $\langle 4 \rangle + \langle 4 \rangle I \notin \mathcal{N}\wp\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}_{12}(I)}$.

(3) In \mathbb{Z} , we have $\langle 9 \rangle \in \wp\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}}$. Therefore, according to Theorem 4.6, it follows that

$$\langle 9 \rangle + \mathbb{Z}I \in \mathcal{N}\wp\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}(I)}.$$

(4) In \mathbb{Z}_{12} , we have $\langle 4 \rangle \in \wp\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}_{12}}$. Therefore, according to Theorem 4.6, it follows that $\langle 4 \rangle + \mathbb{Z}I \in \mathcal{N}\wp\mathfrak{R}_{\mathbb{Z}_{12}(I)}$.

Corollary 4.9 Clearly, every neutrosophic prime ideal is a neutrosophic generalised primary ideal.

Theorem 4.10 Assuming that $R(I)$ is a commutative ring. If $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic generalized primary ideal in $R(I)$, then $\sqrt{J + KI}$ is a prime ideal.

Proof.

Since $R(I)$ is commutative, every prime ideal is completely prime by Corollary 2.11, and every generalized primary ideal is primary by Corollary 4.5. Now, we proceed to prove that the following condition holds:

$\forall s_1 + s_2I, s_3 + s_4I \in R(I); (s_1 + s_2I)(s_3 + s_4I) \in \sqrt{J + KI} \Rightarrow s_1 + s_2I \in \sqrt{J + KI}$ or $s_3 + s_4I \in \sqrt{J + KI}$.

Suppose $s_1 + s_2I \notin \sqrt{J + KI}$.

On the other hand, we have $(s_1 + s_2I)(s_3 + s_4I) \in \sqrt{J + KI} \Rightarrow \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; [(s_1 + s_2I)(s_3 + s_4I)]^n \in J + KI$
 $\Rightarrow (s_1 + s_2I)^n(s_3 + s_4I)^n \in J + KI$

We have $s_1 + s_2I \notin \sqrt{J + KI} \Rightarrow \forall n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (s_1 + s_2I)^n \notin J + KI$. Because $J + KI$ is a neutrosophic primary ideal, there is $m \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ such that $[(s_3 + s_4I)^n]^m \in J + KI$. Therefore, $(s_3 + s_4I)^{nm} \in J + KI$; $nm \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Thus, $s_3 + s_4I \in \sqrt{J + KI} \Rightarrow \sqrt{J + KI} \in N\wp_{R(I)}$.

Remark 4.11 The following diagram illustrates the relationships among generalized primary, primary, prime, completely prime, and radical ideals in both classical and neutrosophic rings, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Relationship between certain types of ideals in classical and neutrosophic rings.

Corollary 4.12 Assume that $R(I)$ is a commutative ring. If $J + KI$ and $S + TI$ are neutrosophic ideals in $R(I)$, then $J + KI$ is primary ideal and $S + TI$ is its radical iff the following conditions are satisfied.

- (1) $J + KI \subseteq S + TI$
- (2) If $s_1 + s_2I \in S + TI$, then there is $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (s_1 + s_2I)^n \in J + KI$.
- (3) If $(s_1 + s_2I)(s_3 + s_4I) \in J + KI$ and $s_1 + s_2I \notin J + KI$, then $s_3 + s_4I \in S + TI$

Proof.

(\Rightarrow): If $J + KI$ is a primary ideal and $S + TI = \sqrt{J + KI}$, then the conditions (1), (2), and (3) are satisfied, according to Theorem 4.10.

(\Leftarrow): $\forall s_1 + s_2I, s_3 + s_4I \in R(I); (s_1 + s_2I)(s_3 + s_4I) \in J + KI$. Assume that $s_1 + s_2I \notin J + KI$; therefore, $s_3 + s_4I \in S + TI$, according to condition (3). Then, by condition (2), there is $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ such that $(s_3 + s_4I)^n \in J + KI$. Thus, $J + KI$ is a primary ideal.

Now, we prove that $S + TI = \sqrt{J + KI}$.

$\forall s_1 + s_2I \in S + TI \Rightarrow \exists n \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (s_1 + s_2I)^n \in J + KI$, according to condition (2). Therefore,

$s_1 + s_2I \in \sqrt{J + KI}$. Thus, $S + TI \subseteq \sqrt{J + KI}$... (i)

On the other hand, $\forall s_3 + s_4I \in \sqrt{J + KI} \Rightarrow \exists m \in \mathbb{Z}^+; (s_3 + s_4I)^m \in J + KI$.

Let m_0 be the smallest positive integer such that $(s_3 + s_4I)^{m_0} \in J + KI$.

If $m_0 = 1$, then $s_3 + s_4I \in J + KI$. Therefore, $s_3 + s_4I \in S + TI$, according to condition (1).

If $m_0 = 2$, then $(s_3 + s_4I)^2 = (s_3 + s_4I)(s_3 + s_4I) \in J + KI$ and $s_3 + s_4I \notin J + KI$. Therefore, $s_3 + s_4I \in S + TI$, according to condition (3).

If $m_0 = 3$, then $(s_3 + s_4I)^3 = (s_3 + s_4I)(s_3 + s_4I)^2 \in J + KI$ and $(s_3 + s_4I)^2 \notin J + KI$. Therefore, $s_3 + s_4I \in S + TI$, according to condition (3).

If $m_0 > 3$, then $(s_3 + s_4I)^{m_0} = (s_3 + s_4I)(s_3 + s_4I)^{m_0-1} \in J + KI$ and $(s_3 + s_4I)^{m_0-1} \notin J + KI$.

Therefore, $s_3 + s_4I \in S + TI$, according to condition (3). Thus, $\sqrt{J + KI} \subseteq S + TI$... (ii)

From (i) and (ii), we conclude that $\sqrt{J + KI} = S + TI$.

Conclusion

In this research, we identified and explored the notions of radical ideals and primary ideals in neutrosophic rings. We examined the fundamental properties of these concepts and proved several theorems related to their characteristics. Various examples were provided to validate the results of this study. Future research will expand the investigation into Noetherian and Artinian neutrosophic rings, including a comprehensive study of their essential properties.

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